

A Study on the Performance of Photovoltaic Panels Dated April 6, 2023

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Abstract

This study examines the energy production performances of photovoltaic (PV) panels placed in different orientations based on data collected on April 6, 2023, in Şanlıurfa. The performance of bifacial (dual-sided) and monofacial (single-sided) panels was compared, and their efficiencies in different orientations were analyzed.

The panel placed on the east-facing side achieved the highest energy production early in the morning; however, this production decreased as the day progressed and the sun changed its position. The rooftop panel reached its maximum energy production during the midday hours when sunlight was at a perpendicular angle, demonstrating the rooftop's potential for efficiently collecting solar energy.

The bifacial panel placed on the south-facing side produced 17.5% more energy compared to the monofacial panel, thanks to the additional radiation it received from its rear surface. These findings indicate that bifacial panels offer higher efficiency and are a suitable option for optimizing energy production. The study also obtained results consistent with similar research in the literature, confirming that these panels operate more efficiently under high albedo conditions.

In conclusion, this study highlights the superiority of bifacial panels in enhancing energy production potential and suggests that these panels should be preferred in PV systems.

1. Introduction

In recent years, photovoltaic (PV) systems have become one of the key components of clean energy production. The direct conversion of solar energy into electrical energy is critical for reducing carbon emissions and achieving energy independence. With the increasing adoption of this technology, studies on how PV panels perform under different conditions have also grown. In particular, analyzing the performance of PV systems under various orientations and meteorological conditions is crucial for developing more efficient energy production strategies.

The energy production capacity of photovoltaic panels depends on various factors. These include solar radiation, ambient temperature, the panel's installation angle, and the type of panel (monofacial or bifacial). Bifacial panels offer higher efficiency compared to monofacial panels by collecting sunlight from both sides.

The literature includes numerous studies that address the performance comparison of bifacial and monofacial PV

panels under different orientations. These studies generally show that bifacial panels perform better under various environmental and installation conditions. In the study by Kivambe et al. [4], the energy efficiency of vertically oriented east-west bifacial PV systems in desert environments was examined, revealing significantly higher efficiency compared to monofacial panels [4]. Similarly, Garrod et al. [2] found comparable results when evaluating the thermal performance of bifacial panels under different albedo conditions [2].

In the systematic literature review conducted by Yakubu et al. [5], it was reported that bifacial panels have a higher energy production potential compared to traditional monofacial panels, with this difference becoming particularly pronounced under high albedo conditions [5]. Additionally, Moreno et al. [3] compared the performance of bifacial and monofacial panels in different climates and found that bifacial panels provide higher efficiency compared to monofacial panels.

This study aims to validate the results found in the literature by analyzing the energy values produced by four

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different PV panels in Şanlıurfa on April 6, 2023, at half-hour intervals. The results are discussed in light of the obtained data and compared with existing studies.

2. Materials and Methods

This study involves an experimental analysis of BIPV (Building-Integrated Photovoltaics) systems installed on different facades of a building under the meteorological conditions in Şanlıurfa on April 6, 2023. For this purpose, photovoltaic (PV) panels were placed on the south, east, and roof areas of the container. A single-sided (monofacial) panel was installed on both the roof and the east facade. On the south facade, both monofacial and dual-sided (bifacial) panels were installed for comparative analysis (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Drawing of the installation in SolidWorks.

The experimental setup was established at the Harran University GAP-YENEV Research and Application Center (Figure 2). The technical specifications of the panels used in the experiment are provided below:

Bifacial Panel: Maximum power: 335 Watts, efficiency: 20.05%, south-facing, transparent glass-glass.

South Monofacial Panel: Maximum power: 335 Watts, efficiency: 20.07%, south-facing, opaque.

Roof Monofacial Panel: Maximum power: 335 Watts, efficiency: 20.07%, horizontal placement, opaque.

East Monofacial Panel: Maximum power: 335 Watts, efficiency: 20.07%, vertical placement, opaque.

Figure 2. Actual image of the installation.

Two panels, consisting of bifacial (dual-sided) and monofacial panels, were installed on the south facade to enable a comparative analysis under the same conditions. Among the panels on the south facade, the one closer to the east facade is the bifacial panel. The panels on the south facade were installed approximately 11.5 cm away from the wall. The wall behind the bifacial panel is covered with aluminum foil to allow sunlight to reach the rear surface of the bifacial panel (Figure 3). Additionally, monofacial PV panels with the same capacity were placed on the east facade and the roof. This setup allows for a comparative examination of the effects on electricity production across different facades.

Figure 3. Illustration of the gap between the panels and the wall on the south facade.

Each panel was connected to the grid via microinverters, and the generated power was recorded by the Data Transfer Unit (DTU) at 15-minute intervals.

3. Results and Discussion

East-Facing Panel: In the early morning, with sunlight directly coming from the east, the east-facing panel achieved the highest energy production. This situation indicates that

maximum irradiation reaches the east-facing panels during the morning hours. This finding is consistent with the results obtained by Kivambe et al. [4] in desert environments. Towards midday, the energy production of the east-facing panel began to decrease as sunlight shifted towards the roof and south-facing directions (Figure 4).

Roof Panel: At midday, when sunlight was coming at a direct angle, the roof panel reached maximum energy production. The rooftop panel generated higher energy throughout the day compared to the other panels. The reason for this is that on April 6, the sunlight came from a higher angle. However, considering that sunlight comes from a more horizontal angle during the winter months, the south-facing orientation should be preferred for higher production (Figure 4).

South-Facing Bifacial and Monofacial Panels: The bifacial panel installed on the south facade produced higher energy throughout the day compared to the monofacial panel. This is due to the bifacial panel's ability to collect sunlight from both of its surfaces.

The reflection of sunlight from the aluminum foil placed on the wall behind the bifacial panel has particularly enhanced the energy production of the bifacial panel. As a result, by the end of the day, the bifacial panel produced an average of 17.5% more energy than the monofacial panel. It

can be noted that the rear surface configurations highlighted in the study by Du et al. [4] are similar to the surface technologies used to optimize sunlight collection.

Overall Assessment: On April 6, 2023, the monofacial panel on the roof achieved higher power output due to the sunlight coming from a higher angle. From this finding, it can be predicted that installing bifacial panels on rooftops could increase electricity production during months when the sun is higher in the sky. However, considering that during the winter months the sunlight comes from a more inclined angle from the south, bifacial panels could be installed on the southern facade to enhance winter performance. It has been observed that bifacial panels generate more energy due to additional radiation received from their rear surface. The albedo effect observed in the study by Garrod et al. [2] also emerges as a factor supporting the superior performance of bifacial panels under Şanlıurfa conditions. This highlights the potential for optimizing energy production when bifacial panels are used in high albedo environments.

The data analysis indicates that the bifacial panel utilizes sunlight more effectively and is particularly more efficient during high radiation periods. Similarly, these results align with the findings of Yakubu et al. [5], which report higher efficiency of bifacial panels under high albedo conditions.

Figure 4. Power generation graph of the panels

4. Conclusions

This study provides a comprehensive evaluation of the performance of four different photovoltaic panels based on data collected on April 6, 2023, in Şanlıurfa. The findings reveal that bifacial panels offer higher efficiency compared to monofacial panels, primarily due to their ability to capture sunlight from both surfaces.

The bifacial panel installed facing south produced 17.5% more energy in one day due to the additional radiation received from the rear surface, significantly increasing the efficiency of the bifacial panel. This finding is consistent with other studies in the literature. Specifically, the work by Kivambe et al. [4] in desert environments and the thermal performance analyses by Garrod et al. [2] under different albedo conditions support the superior performance of bifacial panels.

As a result, this study has shown that bifacial panels offer higher efficiency compared to traditional monofacial panels. Specifically, the use of aluminum foil on the rear wall of the bifacial panel has boosted power production to higher levels. The efficiency can be further increased by utilizing technologies that enhance the albedo effect. These findings are valuable for encouraging the use of bifacial panels in future PV system installations and serve as an important reference for developing energy production strategies.

Declaration of Ethical Standards

“The authors of this article declare that the materials and methods used in this study do not require ethical committee permission and/or legal-special permission.”

Conflict of Interest

“The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.”

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